

Speculation on the Emergence of Tsallis Entropy from a Uniform Distribution Part 2

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In Part I, we suggested that the Tsallis family of entropy, $\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q)$ may be derived from the idea of assigning a very simple uncertainty expression $1-1/n$ to a uniform distribution, where n is the number of outcomes. In other words, $1/n$ is the probability associated with a guessed number for one die toss and $1-1/n$ is the probability this result is not obtained.

We argued that one could consider guessing two numbers associated with two successive die tosses etc and obtained the general result: $1 - \sum_i p_i^q$ where $p_i=1/n$ for a uniform distribution and $q-1$, the number of numbers guessed or die tosses. We further argued that one may divide this value by $q-1$ to put all q 's on the same footing so to speak and showed that for $q=1$, one obtained $\sum_i p_i \ln(p_i)$, Shannon's entropy (multiplied by -1). In other words, the Tsallis family of entropies $\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (q-1)$ follows from trying to find a simple uncertainty expression for a uniform distribution. Here we note that if one maximizes this entropy subject to the constraint: $\sum_n p_i(n)^q$, then $p_i(n)$ is no longer a uniform distribution which is already well-known. We suggest that the uniform distribution gives equal probability to all n values of the die. In other words, n is simply a marking and does not map to a physical quantity which would weight different n values differently. The notion of maximization of entropy is to remove as much information as possible (i.e. create as much uncertainty as possible), but a constraint such as $\sum_i p_i$ imposes a second piece of information, namely that i does carry weight in the constraint. This is a physical consideration we argue, not a mathematical one.

Thus, maximization of the entropy expression (Tsallis form), obtained from considerations of the uniform distribution, does not yield the uniform distribution under a constraint which introduces information, i.e. special treatment of n values. We further note that the $p_i \ln(p_i)$ Shannon's form which results from $q=1$, even in the uniform distribution scenario, is specially linked to the notion of n being quantity because if this is the case, then $n_1+n_2 = n$ total, and $\ln(p_1) + \ln(p_2) = \ln(p_1+p_2)$ implies that $p(n) = C \exp(-n/T)$ for $p(n)$ to drop with n .

Tsallis Entropy

We derived (so to speak) the Tsallis family of entropies:

$$S(\text{Tsallis}) = \{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q) \quad ((1))$$

from considerations of a uniform distribution. Here we change $q-1$ (from Part I) to $1-q$ in order to obtain the usual minus sign appearing in front of an entropy expression. We argued that the Tsallis expression ((1)) appears by seeking a very simple expression which describes uncertainty for a uniform distribution. For a die with n possible outcomes, we suggested that this is:

$$1 - 1/n \quad ((2))$$

This implies that one guesses a number (from 1 to n) and tosses the die once. ((2)) is the probability one does not obtain the guessed number. We generalized this to two guesses with two successive tosses etc and wrote an expression in terms of $p_n = 1/n$:

1- $\sum_i p_i^q$ ((3)) where $q-1$ is the number of numbers guessed

To put all q values on the same footing, so to speak, we divided ((3)) by $(q-1)$, the number of tosses. We then showed that for $q=1$, one obtains the change in probability for $q \rightarrow q + \delta$, i.e. minus Shannon's entropy. If one uses $1-q$ instead of $q-1$, one obtains Shannon's entropy with the correct sign.

As a result, the Tsallis family of entropies, which includes Shannon's entropy for $q=1$:

$$S(\text{Tsallis}) = \{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q) \quad ((4))$$

follows from considerations of a uniform probability distribution.

It may seem curious (at first glance) that maximizing ((4)) subject to the constraint:

$$\sum_i p_i^q = 1 \quad ((5))$$

does not yield the uniform distribution. It yields instead:

$$f(e_i/T) = \{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((6))$$

Here we have replaced i in ((4)) with e_i/T . In other words, i in ((4)) is the variable whereas e_i/T is now the variable with i as a label.

We suggest that there is no issue that one does not obtain the uniform distribution when maximizing entropy subject to ((5)) for the reason that the constraint introduces extra information into the problem. A uniform distribution, such as one associated with a die, implies that all n values have an equal probability. In such a case, n is simply a label and not a physical quantity. The constraint ((5)) suggests that n is actually a quantity and so one cannot have ((5)) associated with a uniform distribution. We thus suggest that the constraint is key to suggesting the physical conditions present. For example, if $q=1$, then ((6)) yields:

$$f(e_i/T) = \exp(-e_i/T), \text{ the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann result } ((7))$$

This is in fact linked with physical single particle energies e_i . Thus, a probability to have e_i , namely $f(e_i/T)$, is directly linked to the value of e_i/T . One does not have two sets of information in the maximization problem yielding $\exp(-e_i/T)$. This is the maximum entropy for this constraint.

One may note that if the various e_i values are not distinguished, i.e. are all considered to be the same, then $\exp(-e_i/T) = \text{constant}$ and one recovers the uniform distribution. Thus, having e_i represent physical quantities means that part of e_i may be transferred as we later argue.

As a result, we suggest that there is no problem deriving (so to speak) the Tsallis entropy form for a uniform probability distribution, but then linking it with another distribution associated with a constraint which represents a different physical weighting scheme than the one linked with a die with n sides, with n simply being labels.

The fact that e_i/T may be a quantity possessed by a particle means that one may have interactions which transfer some e_i from one particle to another. If $f(e_i/T)$ is probability and is conserved and at the same time carries the same information as e_i , then e_i must also be conserved, we argue. This is why one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((8))$$

It is known that an entropy expression may be evaluated using various different probability values. If one maximizes with respect to a constraint, one must be aware that the constraint is linked with particular physical conditions, we argue. In other words, even though one could in fact create the average $\sum_i 1/n = n(n+1)/(2n)$ for a uniform distribution, this is not a constraint, but a consequence of $p_i = 1/n$. Using the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ implies certain physical conditions. The fact that ((8)) is compatible with maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ shows that the constraint is in fact linked with a physical picture of scattering with e_i being a quantity, i.e. single particle energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in Part I, we obtained the Tsallis entropy: $\{1 - \sum_i p_i^q\} / (1-q)$ through considerations of a uniform distribution $p_i = 1/n$. For $q=1$, one obtains Shannon's entropy. Now given an entropy expression, one may insert any set of probabilities one wishes, but these do not necessarily maximize the entropy subject to a constraint. We argue here that if one maximizes Tsallis entropy subject to $\sum_i e_i p_i^q$, one obtains ((6)) and not the uniform distribution. We argue that this is not surprising because a constraint imposes physical reality on the problem. In particular, a uniform distribution $p_i = 1/n$ treats all sides of the die as the same. There is nothing special about one n value versus another. If one, however, introduces the constraint: $\sum_i p_i^q$ (which is average energy for $q=1$), then this is no longer the toss of a die picture because e_i is a physical quantity which may be transferred in two body collisions as we show for the $q=1$ case. Thus, we argue that a constraint is very important from a physical standpoint. We also suggest that there is nothing wrong obtaining the Tsallis entropy with parameter q for a uniform distribution and then using it, together with a constraint, to find a non-uniform distribution which maximizes it, subject to the physical conditions of the constraint.